

SOLID STATE POLYLACTIDE-POLY(METHYL METHACRYLATE) PRECURSORS FOR THE IN-LINE PRODUCTION OF FOAM CORE SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The overall aim of this work is to develop precursors suitable for the in-line production of lightweight bio-based foam core sandwich structures with consolidated wood particle facings, using a non-VOC blowing agent. A preliminary study of poly(D,L-lactide) (PDLA)/CO₂ showed that solid expandable precursors could be prepared by impregnation with CO₂ under both subcritical and supercritical conditions. However, because the particleboard process involves temperatures, T , well above the effective glass transition temperature, T_g , of the PDLA/CO₂, foam collapse tended to occur during consolidation of facings. The PDLA was therefore extrusion-compounded with poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) in order to increase its T_g .

That the thermal characteristics of the PLA could be modified by blending with PMMA was confirmed by differential scanning calorimetric measurements of T_g and the evolution of the corresponding α -transition from dynamic mechanical analysis over a wide range of compositions. The uptake of liquid CO₂ during impregnation at 10 °C and 5 MPa was found to decrease with PMMA content, but the subsequent desorption rates were comparable with those obtained with unmodified PDLA. It was consequently possible to adapt an impregnation and conditioning procedure developed previously for PDLA to give solid granular precursors from PDLA-50 wt% PMMA blends that were stable during handling at room T , but contained sufficient CO₂ for the generation of low density foams at T in the vicinity of 100 °C, as required by the particle-board process, in which water vapour is the primary vector for heat transport.

The free expansion behaviour of the precursors was investigated systematically as a function of T , in order to establish process windows and investigate process-structure-property relationships. Model foam-core particleboard sandwich structures were then successfully prepared using an open hydraulic press and a single thermo-mechanical cycle, in which consolidation of the facings using a conventional binder and foam expansion took place simultaneously.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is currently considerable interest in developing sustainable technologies for the production of bio-sourced, biodegradable polylactide (PLA) foams as an alternative to expanded polystyrene (PS), using environmentally friendly physical blowing agents such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is readily absorbed by PLA in the supercritical and liquid states [1]. The applications of PLA are nevertheless limited by its relatively low glass transition temperature, T_g , and heat deflection T in the amorphous state (about 60 and 50 °C respectively). Efforts to improve the thermal properties of PLA have included stereo complexation [2], filler addition, copolymerization, and blending with relatively high T_g thermoplastics [3]. This latter approach is particularly straightforward and versatile given adequate compatibility between the different blend components [4, 5]. Atactic PMMA is an inexpensive amorphous thermoplastic with T_g typically around 110 °C, depending on its comonomer content and

tacticity. While the behavior of PLA-PMMA blends is strongly dependent on molar mass, the degree of crystallinity of the PLA and the processing conditions, they show at least partial miscibility over a wide range of compositions, and hence composition dependent T_g [5-15]. Moreover, the solubility of CO₂ in PLA-PMMA blends has been found to be sufficient to permit its use as a physical blowing agent for the preparation of low density foams [11, 16].

The present work stems from our interest in using liquid CO₂ to prepare PLA-based foam precursors suitable for the in-line production of foam-core sandwich structures with consolidated wood particle facings, as a sustainable lightweight alternative to conventional particleboard [17, 18]. Ideally, production of foam-core particleboard should be closely based on the conventional particleboard process, which is relatively cost-efficient. The following batch process, illustrated in Figure 1, has been developed to reproduce the essential aspects of the continuous process envisaged for in-line foaming at the laboratory scale [18]. A mat is formed from two layers of adhesive-treated wood particles and a core layer of foam precursors. This mat is then transferred to a hot-press, where heat and pressure are applied in order to cure the wood particle facings. Once T in the core layer has reached the level needed to activate the precursor, the press is opened slightly to give room for the core material to expand. Finally, the panel is cooled and stabilized.

The CO₂ impregnated precursors are required to take the form of pellets or granules that are: (i) sufficiently stable under ambient conditions to allow straightforward handling; (ii) expand to form low density foams over a range of times and T consistent with the process window for the consolidation of the facings. Preliminary work has shown the relatively low T_g of unmodified PLA to lead to inadequate foam stability under these latter conditions. We have therefore investigated the use of PLA-PMMA foam precursors prepared by melt blending and impregnation with liquid CO₂ as a means of adjusting the effective foaming T . In what follows, we describe the basic physical properties of these precursors, results from preliminary studies of their thermally induced foaming behavior, and their integration into a laboratory-scale simulation of the foam-core particleboard process.

Figure 1: Simulated in-line particleboard production steps: (a) three layered mat fabrication, (b) surface layer consolidation and (c) foam precursor expansion and cooling [18].

2 EXPERIMENTAL

A commercial grade of poly(D,L-lactide) (PDLLA) containing 11.6 % D-isomer and with a weight average molar mass, M_w of 320'000 g/mol, was obtained in pellet form from NatureWorks LLC. It was nominally amorphous, although residual crystallinity was observed after prolonged annealing treatments, for example. An injection molding grade of atactic PMMA (density 1.19 g/cm³, $M_w \approx 100'000$ g/mol) was provided by Evonik Industries AG in pellet form. T_g was determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, TA Instruments Q100) heating scans at 10 K/min on 4 to 6 mg specimens to be 58.3 and 110.3 °C for the PDLLA and PMMA respectively. 99.5 % pure CO₂ from Carbagas AG was used as the blowing agent and a general-purpose grade of talc from Fisher Scientific was used as a nucleating agent for the foaming studies.

A twin-screw extruder (Prism TSE 16, Thermo Electron Corporation, 16 mm barrel diameter, L/D ratio of 15:1) was used to prepare PDLLA-PMMA blends with different compositions. The feed, melt and metering T were set to 190, 220 and 210 °C, respectively and the screw speed was 30 RPM. Prior to processing, the PDLLA was dried overnight at 40 °C in a vacuum oven and the PMMA was dried for at least 2 hr at 90 °C in a convection oven. After blending and pelletizing, the blends were stored in

a freezer at -20 °C.

The as-received and blended pellets were dried and compression molded into 1 mm thick discs with a diameter of 25 mm using a hot press (Fontijne TP 50 with 255 × 255 mm² heating platens). In each case, the pellets were placed between polyimide release films in a stainless steel mold and held at 200 °C for 5 min. A nominal hydraulic force of 6 kN, equivalent to a pressure of 0.25 MPa, was then applied at the same temperature for a further 5 min, after which the platens were cooled under pressure to room temperature over approximately 10 min using the integrated water cooling system. 0.5 to 0.6 mm thick films were prepared for dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA, TA instruments Q800) using the same procedure. Strips cut from the films were subjected to heating scans from 25 to 150 °C at 3 K/min with a 0.05 % sinusoidal deformation in tensile mode at a frequency of 1 Hz.

Impregnation of the compression molded discs with liquid CO₂ was carried out at approximately 5 MPa and 10 °C using a high pressure chamber from Autoclave France equipped with a cooling system. Once the required impregnation time had elapsed, the pressure was released at a rate of 0.01 MPa/sec in each case. After depressurization, certain specimens were immediately transferred to a high precision balance and the mass loss due to desorption of the CO₂ monitored as a function of time at 21 °C [17]. Foaming was carried out by immersing the impregnated discs in a thermostatically controlled silicone oil bath and allowing them to undergo free expansion and equilibrate at the *T* of the bath. The resulting morphologies were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Philips XLF30-FEG).

Sandwich panels were produced from a mat of adhesive-treated wood particles and PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA precursor pellets containing 1 wt% talc, using a Höfer HLP210, as described in the introduction. The precursor was produced directly from the twin-screw extruder, using a pelletizer to produce 1 to 1.5 mm diameter granules, and impregnated by immersion in liquid CO₂ at 5 MPa and 10 °C for 30 min, followed by conditioning for a further 2 hours at ambient pressure and 10 °C. For the facings, dried wood particles were mixed with 12 wt% of an adhesive prepared from urea-formaldehyde resin with 3 wt% ammonium persulfate as a curing agent.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal and mechanical properties of the blends

DSC heating scans from 20 to 230 °C and 10 K/min (Figure 2 and Table 1) indicated the extruded and compression molded specimens to be substantially amorphous. The as-extruded blends showed two glass transitions during the first heating cycle, whose estimated mid-points are given as T_{g1} and T_{g2} in Table 1 with the subscript 2 denoting the higher transition *T*. The blends with the lowest PDLLA contents also showed a strong exothermic peak immediately above T_{g1} owing to physical aging, possibly masking a second glass transition in certain cases. However, a single, albeit relatively broad glass transition was observed at all compositions during subsequent cooling from 250 to 20 °C at 10 K/min and in the second heating cycle, as also shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: First and second DSC heating scans of the as-extruded PDLLA-PMMA blends.

The various glass transition temperatures have been plotted as a function of PMMA content in Figure 3 for the as-extruded blends. T_{g1} showed a significant but relatively small increase over T_g for pure PDLLA as the PMMA content increased, while T_{g2} increased by around 45 K as the PMMA content increased from 40 to 100 wt%, indicating partial miscibility in the as-extruded specimens [19]. On the other hand, the observation of a single glass transition on cooling from 230 °C and during second heating cycle implied complete miscibility, the evolution of T_{g12} with PMMA content suggesting strong plasticization by the PDLLA. These results were broadly consistent with literature results for blends of polylactides with PMMA of comparable M_w after thermal cycling [12, 14, 15]. It is hence concluded that this system shows an upper critical solution temperature (UCST) above 200 °C, depending on molar mass, composition and tacticity, such that initially phase-separated blends show a single DSC T_g on cycling to $T > \text{UCST}$ [12, 13]. In the present case, the initial compounding procedure, for which the maximum extrusion temperature and drying conditions were chosen to limit degradation of the PLA, was inadequate to give initially homogeneous blends, and, similarly, double glass transitions persisted in the compression molded specimens, albeit somewhat shifted with respect to those seen in the as-extruded blends (Table 1).

	wt% PMMA	T_{g1} [°C]	T_{g2} [°C]	T_{g12} [°C]
Extruded PDLLA/PMMA	0		58.4	58.4
	20	60.3	-	59.7
	40	60.9	78.1	63.3
	60	66.5	81.6	72.3
	80	71.5	95.7	93.1
	100		110.0	110.0
Compression molded PDLLA/PMMA	0		57.5	57.5
	20	55.3	-	58.3
	40	61.0	84.5	63.3
	60	68.9	-	72.82
	80	-	88.3	92.7
	100		109.6	109.6

Table 1: Thermal transitions determined from the first and second DSC heating scans for the as-extruded and compression molded PDLLA-PMMA blends

Figure 3: Variation of T_{g1} , T_{g2} and T_{g12} with composition in the as-extruded PDLLA-PMMA blends.

DMA heating scans from compression molded films of the pure resins and PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA showed clear α -transitions, with a marked peak in $\tan \delta$ at 86 °C for PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA and 71 and 126 °C for PDLLA and PMMA, respectively. Consistent with the observation of two glass transitions in the PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA moldings at about 66 and 85 °C in DSC scans, the DMA transition was in this case characterized by a small drop in storage modulus at about 65 °C, followed by a more substantial decrease in modulus corresponding to the main peak in $\tan \delta$ as T increased further. It follows that the mechanical transition was dominated by the response of the PMMA-rich phase.

3.2 CO₂ impregnation and desorption behavior

Impregnation for at least 3 hr in liquid CO₂ at 5 MPa and 10 °C was generally necessary for the CO₂ content of the compression molded discs to reach saturation in so far as the specimen masses evolved little after longer impregnation times. The equilibrium CO₂ contents under the present impregnation conditions were hence estimated to be 42 g/g and 27 g/g for the neat PDLLA and PMMA respectively, and were found to vary approximately linearly with PMMA content at intermediate compositions, consistent with a simple rule of mixtures for the gas solubility in this system [20]. While pure PMMA remained relatively stable on heating to 21 °C after impregnation, PDLLA and the various blends showed significant foaming, accompanied by rapid desorption of the CO₂ (Figure 4) particularly at high PDLLA contents, where PDLLA-rich regions presumably formed a continuous phase [21]. Thus, blends with intermediate compositions showed the lowest CO₂ contents after desorption for 1 hr, owing to both their reduced overall CO₂ contents at saturation and the effect of foaming.

Figure 4: CO₂ desorption from compression molded discs of the PDLLA-PMMA blends and the pure resins.

The instability of the saturated precursors against foaming at 21 °C was attributed to a reduction in T_g in the presence of high concentrations of CO₂ [17, 22, 23]. It was therefore necessary to limit the overall CO₂ content by partial impregnation in liquid CO₂ at 5 MPa and 10 °C, followed by conditioning at 10 °C at ambient pressure in order to reduce the concentration gradients within the specimens [17, 24]. Thus impregnation for 30 min followed by conditioning for 2 hours led to CO₂ contents of 17 and 13 g/g in compression molded discs of the PDLLA and PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA blends, respectively. On the other hand, 2 hours impregnation followed by conditioning for 2 hours resulted in PMMA precursors containing only about 8 g/g CO₂, although this was still sufficient to produce low density foams (see section 3.3). In each case, the reduced CO₂ contents resulted in precursors that were stable during handling at ambient pressure and T . No further attempt was made in the present work to adjust the impregnation conditions in order to obtain comparable CO₂ concentrations in the different materials, although it should be borne in mind that the CO₂ content may have a significant influence on the subsequent foaming behavior, and hence on the final cell morphologies and mechanical properties.

3.3 Foaming behavior

For the initial foaming tests, compression molded discs were prepared from PDLLA, PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA and PMMA containing 1 wt% of talc, which was added to the formulations during extrusion in order to promote foam cell nucleation and hence homogeneous morphologies. These were partially impregnated with liquid CO₂, as described in the previous section, and foamed by immersion in silicone oil at different T , as described in section 2, to give morphologies such as that in Figure 5. The foam expansion ratios were calculated from the ratio of the matrix polymer density, ρ , and the foam density, ρ^* . As seen from Figure 6, PDLLA showed a maximum expansion ratio at about 80 °C, while for the PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA blend and PMMA this maximum shifted to about 100 and 130 °C respectively. As these temperatures were 20 to 30 degrees above T_g in each case, there was a progressive trend towards more open-cell structures and eventually foam collapse as T was raised further. While care should be taken in comparing the absolute values of the expansion ratios among the different materials for the reasons given at the end of section 3.2, they generally corresponded to foam densities in the range 20 to 100 kg/m³, which was considered to offer sufficient scope for optimization for the final application.

Figure 5: SEM micrograph of cellular structure in PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA after foaming at 100 °C.

Figure 6: Expansion ratio after free expansion of PDLLA, PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA and PMMA at various foaming T and for the impregnation/conditioning conditions shown.

The CO_2 content of the pelletized PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA precursors was estimated to be 10 g/g for the same impregnation conditions as used for the compression molded discs. The initially clear pellets became opaque after depressurization and conditioning, suggesting some void formation, but they were generally sufficiently stable to permit handling and dispersion in the three-layered mat at room temperature without premature expansion. The press time and T in the second process step illustrated in Figure 1 were crucial for the quality of the end product. For the specimen shown in Figure 7, the nominal T of the press was 110 °C, corresponding to a core layer T of approximately 90 °C after 80 s in the press. Under these conditions, the facings were fully cured and the solid precursors showed significant expansion after step 3, and the resulting overall density, 300 kg/m³, was about half of that of conventional particleboard (600 – 700 kg/m³) for a comparable overall thickness of about 19 mm. Mechanical testing and more detailed morphological characterization of the foam-core particles boards is currently in progress.

Figure 7: A PDLLA-50 wt% PMMA foam-core sandwich structure with consolidated wood particle facings produced in an open press.

4 CONCLUSION

Laboratory-scale tests have confirmed that it is feasible to produce foam-core sandwich structures with consolidated wood particle facings in a one-step process using CO₂ as a physical blowing agent for the core. Partial impregnation of extrusion-blended PDLLA/50 wt% PMMA granulates with liquid CO₂ at 5 MPa and 10 °C for 30 min followed by conditioning for 2 hours at 10 °C and ambient pressure resulted in foam precursors that remained stable during handling under ambient conditions, but showed significant expansion at T consistent with those required for consolidation of the wood particle facings. Approximately 19 mm thick foam-core panels were produced in an open press, foaming taking place during partial opening of the press at the end of the cycle. There is clearly considerable scope for optimization of this process, not only through systematic modification of the process parameters (press T and time, moisture content of the wood particles), but also through further optimization of the precursor properties. For example, reducing the size of the precursor granules should allow for a more uniform interface between the core and the facings, provided the impregnation conditions are adjusted to take into account the modified diffusion distances. Detailed characterization of the morphology and mechanical properties of the panels is currently underway, with emphasis on the bonding between the core and the facings.

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